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REGIONAL REPORT ON SOCIAL EXCLUSION AND SOCIAL ECONOMY INITIATIVES IN RURAL AREAS

Pinares Burgos-Soria – Spain

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1. Introduction

The aim of this report is to provide a social and economic diagnosis of rural areas and the rural populations of the Spanish ESIRA partner areas. These reports will act as the basis of D4.1, “Benchmark study on social exclusion in rural areas,” and D4.2, “multi-level analysis of social economy initiatives in rural areas”. The report integrates the available literature at the regional/national level as well as statistical data. However, it includes qualitative information coming from key informants in each area. This is a very valuable resource as it allows us to explore the regions' situations and the drivers behind the possible social and economic disadvantages. Thus, it analyses the situation of people living in rural areas, focusing on territorial inequalities. A deeper overview of the drivers of vulnerability and social exclusion in rural contexts has been done in Pinares Burgos-Soria region. The analysis considers the social processes in the region and the livelihood opportunities at the municipal level. Existing assets and hidden resources in the municipality were assessed according to statistical data and the opinions of the leading local social economy stakeholders.

2. Methodology

This report has used a mixed approach that combines quantitative and qualitative data. The quantitative data is secondary information already elaborated coming from official organizations such as the National Statistical Institute (INE) for the elaboration and construction of information. On the other hand, the tools used within the framework of the qualitative methodology were the following:

1) Documentary and socio-historical analysis

To prepare the document, an intense literature review has been carried out in databases of interest: Dialnet (especially for publications in Spanish), Scopus and Web of Sciences. Different search syntaxes were constructed involving terms of interest for the report: vulnerability, territory, social exclusion, Europe, Spain, employment demand, social services, entrepreneurship, and rurality. From the first results, specific literature searches were organized based on the first references consulted. Among the resources used, academic articles, book chapters, and NGO reports on issues related to ESIRA stand out.

2) In-depth interviews, group interviews and walking-interviews

Considering all the qualitative tools used for acquiring higher knowledge on the socioeconomic situation of the pilot area, all the information provided by them has been of great relevance for elaborating the report. Besides, group interviews (those conducted at the beginning) were conducted virtually with a group of stakeholders linked to the territory. At least 30 group interviews were conducted having a heterogenous representation of the main stakeholders considered: local authorities, representatives of social services and different cultural and social entities, as well as some enterprises (tourism, economic or cultural). Secondly, individual in-depth interviews were conducted with key informants. It is relevant to mention that in all cases they were open interviews, without a structured script and only with global axes focused on the socioeconomic diagnosis of the territory (Vasilachis de Gialdino, 2005). Finally, during the presentations of the ESIRA project in the localities,

observation together with informal information (those produced during coffee-break or at the end of the sessions) with participants were of great interest having better knowledge about their concerns, interests and needs (King and Woodroffe, 2017).

As already mentioned, quantitative data was collected from the National Institute of Statistics (INE) in the case of Spain, and data was provided by Eurostat. In these cases, tables have been constructed with statistical information from these sources and with a strictly descriptive character.

3. Country overview: Spain

3.1 Territorial system of the country

In terms of the territorial system, Spain has a multi-tiered territorial system comprising Autonomous Communities, Provinces, and Municipalities. The country is divided into 17 Autonomous Communities (Figure 1), each endowed with a certain degree of legislative and executive autonomy. Within these communities, there are 50 provinces that serve as administrative divisions and are further subdivided into municipalities. Municipalities are the basic local units that obtain their own political structure and government. In addition to the Autonomous Communities, Spain also includes two distinct Autonomous Cities, Ceuta and Melilla, located on the northern coast of Africa. These cities, although not part of the 17 Autonomous Communities, have a special status and a level of legislative and executive autonomy.

Figure 1: Spanish territorial distribution at the regional level

Source: www.mappr.co/counties/spain/

The politics between all these levels implies a complex distribution of power and responsibilities. Autonomous Communities have acquired considerable self-governance, which means managing crucial issues such as education and healthcare. On the other hand, Provinces and Municipalities play a relevant role in local administration, which means they have a direct impact on rural people's daily lives. This intricate system balances centralised and decentralised governance, reflecting Spain's diverse cultural and regional identities. Figure 2 provides an overlook of the territorial distribution of Castilla y León provinces.

Figure 2: Spanish territorial distribution at sub-regional level. The autonomous Community of Castile and Leon

Source: [Geography | About Castilla y León | Junta de Castilla y León](#)

3.2 Strategies and policies

In recent years, different policies, instruments, and initiatives have been implemented at the national level to support local development in rural areas. The more relevant areas as follows:

- **The National Recovery, Transformation, and Resilience Plan:** this plan was launched in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, having a focus on rural economy modernization through investments in digital infrastructure, sustainability, and rural development. Spain is one of the major beneficiaries of the Facility, receiving 163 billion euros, including 84 billion euros in loans, for the period 2021-2026. The Plan is based on four transversal axes: Ecological transition, digital transformation, territorial and social cohesion, and gender equality; it is organised into ten lever policies that include 31 lines of action. A key part of this plan has focused on the investment in digitalisation and connectivity in rural areas, reducing the digital gap as, before the pandemic, many areas of the rural territories had even a poor mobile connectivity and, thus, a very scarce internet connection. The plan also emphasises sustainable agriculture practices, aligning with Spain's goals of reducing carbon emissions and promoting environmental stewardship in rural areas.
- **The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Strategic Plans 2023-2027:** this plan is aligned with the broader EU objectives, although it is tailored to the specific needs of the Spanish agricultural sector. The plan focuses on enhancing the resilience of the sector by supporting small and medium-sized farms, improving food security, and promoting environmental sustainability. One of the key elements has been the implementation of eco-schemes, which provide incentives for farmers to adopt practices that benefit the environment, such as organic farming, carbon sequestration, and biodiversity preservation. Spain's plan also places a strong

emphasis on climate action, aiming to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture and improve water management. (Ministry of Agriculture Fisheries and Food (Spain). (w.d.).).

- **The Leader Programme:** LEADER has been crucial in combating rural depopulation and promoting economic diversification in rural areas. This community-led development approach has enabled Local Action Groups to implement projects that are tailored to the specific needs of their communities (The pilot region includes four LAGs) These projects have ranged from supporting small businesses and rural tourism to preserving cultural heritage and promoting renewable energy. The LEADER Programme has been particularly successful in revitalizing rural areas by creating jobs and fostering social cohesion.
- **National Rural Development Program 2014-2020:** Spain's National Rural Development Program for 2014-2020 focused on addressing the challenges faced by rural areas, particularly in agriculture and forestry. The program's priorities included improving the competitiveness of the agricultural sector, promoting sustainable forest management, and enhancing the quality of life in rural areas. It also supported entrepreneurship and innovation in rural communities, which has led to the creation of new businesses and job opportunities. The program played a critical role in advancing Spain's sustainability goals, particularly through initiatives aimed at reducing environmental impact and adapting to climate change, according to the new LEADER Program 2023-2027.

Regarding social inclusion, at the national level, there are some other instruments that have been implemented in rural areas. There are as follows:

- **Spanish Business Confederation of the Social Economy (CEPES):** this Organisation includes a good range of social economy entities such as cooperatives, labour societies, foundations and so on. It promotes cooperative enterprises that empower communities and ensure economic sustainability in rural areas.
- **Integrated Territorial Investments (ITI):** This EU instrument supports integrated actions in specific areas to address local needs and challenges, fostering balanced development and promoting social inclusion in rural regions.

Local Social Services and Infrastructure Development: National and regional governments enhance rural social services and infrastructure by funding healthcare centres, educational facilities, and community spaces to foster social cohesion.

3.3 Territorial inequalities in Spain

Regarding Spanish disadvantaged regions, and according to the European Anti-Poverty and Social Exclusion Network in the Spanish State (EAPN-ES), the **Southern regions** show higher rates of poverty and social exclusion. For instance, attending to data from 2023, the AROPE rate (which measures the population at risk of poverty or social exclusion) reached 37.5% in Southern areas (highest in Andalusia, the Canary Islands, Murcia, and Extremadura), contrasting with the lowest ones in the Northern regions. Castilla and Leon AROPE rate for 2023 is 22.4.

Economic disparities are also clear when the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita and unemployment rates are analysed; social participation and educational results also reveal a north-south gap. In the case of Castilla and León, the region faces other challenges regarding, above all, the progressively declining population of rural (but also some urban) areas, ageing, and economic disparities that need urgent interventions for sustainable growth (Colino et al., 2020). However, the unemployment rate for Castile and Leon in 2023 has been the lowest (9.1%) compared to Spain (12.1%); together with the per capita income, very similar to the Spanish average.

On the other hand, the territorial characteristics of disadvantaged territories are widely heterogeneous. Many disadvantaged territories are in **mountainous areas** that often face challenges in terms of accessibility, infrastructure development, economic opportunities, and depopulation. Disadvantaged territories are frequently characterised by their **rurality and remoteness**, and most of the areas in central Spain could be considered like that, experimenting with remote villages and towns with serious difficulties in mobility issues and access to basic services. Meanwhile, some **coastal areas**, especially those with limited economic activities, may face challenges like unemployment due to seasonal employment fluctuation and a lack of diversified industries. Territories at the **country's periphery or near borders** may face economic challenges due to reduced connectivity, lower investment, and limited market access. Finally, the **islands** can face economic challenges due to their isolation, high dependence on tourism, and logistical difficulties in transport.

However, one of the main territorial disadvantages is the gap between urban and rural areas, being depopulation one of the main challenges that Spanish rural territories (especially located in central Spain) are facing. Economic activity and services are highly concentrated in cities, causing disparities in healthcare provision, education access, and other essential services. Besides, there exist differences in **Infrastructure and Access to Services**. Healthcare Access: Remote and rural areas have limited access to healthcare due to fewer medical facilities and professionals. Educational Opportunities: Rural and economically disadvantaged areas often have limited educational resources, impacting outcomes and social mobility (Oliva & Sanz, 2024).

According to Canals et al. (2023), 26.5% of the Spanish population (12.7 million people) is at risk of poverty and/or social exclusion. In 2019-2023, the number of people living in social exclusion conditions rose to 400,000. Considering these data, the country is far from the 2030 Agenda's main objectives and features.

It is important to highlight two issues that nuance these numbers. Firstly, the characteristics of the indicator, the AROPE (At Risk of Poverty and Exclusion) rate, are elaborated at the European level with official statistical data from each country. In Spain, the AROPE data are compiled with the results of the National Survey of Living Conditions (INE).

The AROPE rate is a very interesting indicator for defining the social situation. This is because it addresses the question of exclusion in an inter-sectional way: poverty, job stability, and income (as seen in Figure 3). In other words, this absolute number has nuances linked to these dimensions, as will be seen below.

Figure 3. The population at risk of poverty or social exclusion. Intersections between sub-populations

Source: INE. Living Conditions Survey (LCS). Press Release February 2024

On the other hand, Spain is a country in which the welfare state has maintained a redistributive role that has allowed it to maintain the quality of life. The report by Canals et al. (2023) points out the improvement in the living conditions of 10.6 million people. In this sense, and as a multidimensional aspect, it is important to observe the elements that form part of these living conditions. When considering the Human Development Index (hereafter HDI), it is possible to consider the condition of this indicator based on its main dimensions.

3.4 Social economy in Spain

The Law 5/2011 on Social Economy, approved by the Spanish Parliament in 2011 is the main milestone of the institutional political recognition of a sector and a business model that employs more than 1,350,000 people, representing 8% of people occupied. Besides, more than 80,000 entities and companies work in that sector, being very significant the number of volunteers that are enrolled in them. This standard indicates the type of organizations that fall under the social economy. According to this document, in the 1970s and 1980s, cooperatives, mutual societies, foundations and associations followed one another in various European countries, with declarations characterizing the identification of the social economy around different principles. The Law, recovers and maintains that “the set of entities not belonging to the public sector that, with democratic operation and management and equal rights and duties of the members, practice a special regime of ownership and distribution of profits, using the surpluses of the fiscal year for the growth of the entity and improvement of the services to the community” (Preamble). Thus, Law 5/2011 indicates in Article 5 that the entities that form part of the social economy are cooperatives, mutual societies, foundations and associations that carry out

economic activity, labour companies, insertion companies, special employment centres, fishermen's guilds, agricultural transformation societies and singular entities created by specific regulations that are governed by the principles established in the previous article.

The idea of Social Economy in Spain is closely linked to the European tradition and is based on the Charter of Principles of the Social Economy in 2002 of the European Conference of Cooperatives, Mutual Societies, Associations and Foundations (CEP-CEMAF), the predecessor of the current European association of social economy (Social Economy Europe). Regarding the representation of different sectors, it has significant relevance in the care and social services area (43%), as well as in the culture and leisure sector (35.2%); in the education sector represents 26% of the organisations while reduces its representation in, agriculture (12.8%) and energy and water sector (10.9%) (CEPES, 2023).

Social enterprises comprehend a vast array of organisations, including cooperatives, work integration social enterprises (WISEs), and fair-trade businesses, contributing significantly to the economy and social cohesion.

3.4.1 A brief history of Spanish social economy

The cooperative movement began in Spain at the late 19th century, focusing on improving conditions for workers and farmers. Mutual aid societies provided social security to members, laying the groundwork for modern social enterprises. However, under Franco's dictatorship (1939-1975), many social organisations were suppressed, surviving some cooperatives that operated under restrictions. It is not until the transition to democracy in the late 1970s when the cooperatives movement is revitalised. The Spanish Constitution of 1978 recognised their role, and worker cooperatives gained prominence, particularly in regions such as the Basque Country and Catalonia.

3.5 Social enterprises

3.5.1 The main legal forms adopted by social enterprises

According to EC (2024), "France, Italy, Spain and Finland account for the largest cooperative sectors in terms of turnover, predominantly driven by agricultural, consumer and worker cooperatives" (p. 15). Social enterprises encompass various forms, such as cooperatives, which include worker cooperatives (owned and operated by employees), consumer cooperatives (owned by customers), and agricultural cooperatives (owned by farmers). Work Integration Social Enterprises (WISEs) focus on integrating disadvantaged individuals into the workforce through training and employment opportunities. Special Employment Centers employ many people with disabilities, providing them with suitable job opportunities. Associations and foundations are non-profit entities that engage in economic activities to support their social missions. Also, mutual societies offer their members social services and benefits like healthcare and pensions. All these organisations contribute significantly to the economy and social cohesion based on the principles determined by the Law. Article 5 of the already referred Law states that "the social economy includes cooperatives, mutual societies, foundations and associations that carry out economic activities, labour companies, insertion companies, special employment centres,

fishermen's guilds, agricultural transformation companies and singular entities created by specific rules that are governed by the established principles (...)"

Regarding social enterprises as it is said in EC (2020), "in Spain, there is no formal definition of what constitutes a social enterprise, and this concept has scarcely been used in public discourse, policy and society in general" (p. 23). Nevertheless, this is changing nowadays. That's why the media started using the concept, discussing experiences and presenting successful entrepreneurs. On the contrary, the social economy concept still prevails in the public discourse. As this document says, "there is a conceptual debate in Spain about the relationship between the concepts of social economy and social enterprise. During the emergence of the social enterprise concept in the country, competition was observed between i) organisations supporting the social economy and ii) social entrepreneurs' support organisations and other advocacy associations not self-included in the social economy sector. The former felt that cooperatives, WISEs, mutual insurance organisations, foundations or associations (all related to the social economy field) could be defined as social enterprises. The latter often preferred not to be linked to the traditional social economy sector and perceived themselves as comprising an innovative field with new rules" (EC, 2020, p.23).

According to the Spanish Confederation of Social Economy Enterprises (CEPES), Spain has approximately 43,000 social enterprises. These enterprises employ around 2.2 million people, representing about 12% of the total employment in Spain.

Social enterprises in Spain engage in a variety of activities. Some of the most common activities are as follows: Agriculture and Food Production (NACE Code A), Manufacturing (NACE Code C), Retail and Wholesale Trade (NACE Code G), Health and Social Work (NACE Code Q), Education (NACE Code P), Accommodation and Food Services (NACE Code I), Arts, Entertainment, and Recreation (NACE Code R).

3.5.2 National strategy/framework to support social enterprises

- Law on Social Economy (Ley de Economía Social) 2011: Provides a comprehensive legal framework for social enterprises, recognizing their role in economic and social development.
- Support Programs and Funding: Various government initiatives and EU funds, including grants, loans, and subsidies, are available to support social enterprises.
- Public Policies and Action Plans: Specific policies aimed at promoting social economy enterprises, such as the Spanish Social Economy Strategy 2023-2027 (EEES), which outlines actions to enhance their growth and impact.

Social enterprises contribute to local development and address the needs of vulnerable people providing benefits in: **Job Creation, Economic Inclusion, Community Services, Sustainable Development, Social Cohesion.**

4. Regional overview – Pinares Burgos-Soria Region

4.1 The main characteristics of the territory

4.1.1 Geographical aspects

The region chosen for the study is called "Pinares Burgos-Soria" and belongs to the autonomous community of Castilla y León in the Northern area on central Spain. It covers two of the nine provinces included in the region: Burgos and Soria. Territorially, it is surrounded by the Sierra de la Demanda, a mountainous range in the Iberian System (see Figure 4). Two main landscapes allow us to identify its geographical personality: the mountain landscape and the pine forests. In fact, it is the largest pine forest area in Spain, covering more than 100,000 hectares. Besides, regarding population, the area includes a total amount of 100 municipalities, some of which have fewer than 100 inhabitants.

This region has suffered intense population exodus for the last decades, especially since 1960 after the intensive industrialisation process. However, the arrival of migrants over the last two decades has favoured the maintenance of the population in larger localities, a migrant population that is largely feminised, helping to balance the high male rates in rural areas. According to the data provided by the National Institute of Statistics (INE) in the last Census 2021, the main demography features are shown in the next Table. Besides, the diagnosis included in the LEADER Plan 2024-2027 elaborated by the LAGs and to be implemented at the Pinares territory has been of great help to provide a more precise socioeconomic framework.

Figure 4. Map of the Pinares Burgos-Soria region

Source: [Aqalsa: Saw of "The Demanda"](#)

The following table (Table 1) shows how one of the main demographic problems in the area is the exodus of young talent and women, who leave these rural areas in search of better job opportunities in nearby cities such as Burgos or Soria or even in Madrid (which is at two and a half hours distance by car). Besides, the ageing population and a very low birth rate are also some of the more relevant demographic features.

Table 1. Main demographic features

Surface area	25,083 km ²
Total Population	24,665
Population density	6.54
Men representation	54.7%
Women representation	45.3%
Population under 16	7.8%
Population over 65	33.7%
Population born in a foreign country	8.3%

Sources: INE, 2021; Agalsa, 2024

However, migration plays a relevant role in the population transformation of the area since female migration is more significant than male, and the age of those who have moved to the territory is much younger than the local population. According to their origin, there is a high presence of people from Eastern Europe (Bulgaria and Rumania), as well as from Latin America; in this case, the population are mainly women who work in the care of the elderly at their own houses.

4.1.2 Economic situation

The primary sector is mainly devoted to agriculture and livestock farming. Much of this agriculture has been adapted to the livestock cycle in the mountainous areas. In the Soria area, the economy has mainly been based on the wood processing industry due to the relevance of the forest. According to Agalsa (2024), in 2020, the rate of people employed in this sector was 13.5%, much higher than the average for Castilla y León (7.7%). But some municipalities stand out above all in which more than 35% of active people are working in the primary sector. On the other hand, the industrial sector represents 17% of occupied, a lower representation compared to the regional average, probably due to the strong industrial weight of the provincial capitals, Burgos and Soria, which are very close to the territory. The main industry found in the territory is the exploitation of natural resources such as stone and wood. In some localities, such as Pradoluengo, there can be found textile industrial oriented to sock making. Finally, the service sector is by far the largest sector in the territory (60%), and it is mainly linked to the large centres of population within the territory, such as Salas de los Infantes, and also related to some relevant features of tourist interest, such as the Atapuerca archaeological sites or the Pilgrims' Route to Santiago de Compostela, among others.

The per capita income of the territory is almost 15,000 euros, but the range of the municipalities varies from 18,107 euros in Villafranca de los Montes de Oca and 12,433 euros in Salas de los Infantes.

Besides, it is interesting to point out that ninety percent of the territory has a good internet coverage, although fibre optic network is still scarce.

4.1.3 Touristic resources

Pinares' tourist resources can be divided into two main groups: natural heritage, and the cultural heritage inherited from previous populations and historical moments. Both have great diversity throughout the territory. In the first case, one of the greatest attractions of the region is the Pico San Millán, the highest peak in the province. The rest of the peaks of the different mountain ranges within the territory, such as the Mencilla, where the old ski resort was located. There are also internationally outstanding cultural elements already mentioned such as the Atapuerca Archaeological Site, declared a World Heritage Site by UNESCO in 2000. Close to this element there can be found the transit of pilgrims on the well-known Camino de Santiago, also a World Heritage Site. There is also a diversity of Assets of Cultural Interest (ACI) scattered throughout the territory, among which we find Historical including Historic Sites such as Covarrubias or Santo Domingo de Silos, and 15 Monuments, some of them within these Sites. In recent years, municipalities and other supra entities of the area have made a big effort to develop forest trails (walking and bike) as well as better access and maintenance of the relevant historical sites.

4.1.4 Institutional setting

In the Pinares region, local mayors, together with rural development technicians and Local Action Groups (LAGs) and regional government officers, are the most relevant actors at the institutional level. These institutions bridge community needs and broader strategies, adapting policies to their specific regions; regarding daily issues, mayors and people working at the local level are the most aware of rural needs and priorities. Their main responsibilities include different actions such as the identification of local priorities, promotion of citizen participation, resource coordination and so on aligned with regional and national development objectives. However, the design and management of local development policy is also embedded in a rather complex framework of multi-level entities whose responsibility and degree of political action is quite diverse. Firstly, at the municipal level, the actions promoted are linked to the facilitation of basic services such as the provision and improvement of certain facilities (sewer system, local building provisions...). At this level, the budget is usually reduced and highly dependent on the municipality's own resources (usually coming from the public forest exploitation), challenging the promotion of relevant actions such as housing, which has become one of the main bottlenecks in rural development. At a second level, the associations of municipalities are responsible for the direct management of certain services such as waste collection. Besides, the Local Action Groups represent clearly one of the main actors in rural development policy in this area, due to their implication in the area as well as the scarcity of collective entities/associations oriented to the socio-economic promotion of the area. Working in the field since the mid-1990s, the aim of these LAGs is the social and economic promotion of the area, focusing mainly on business entrepreneurship, and paying special attention to tourism; as described in the regional report, the area shows a great mountain landscape so that the environmental conservation is a key factor in rural development. Having the area face a depopulation challenge, the LAGs in the area also address the promotion of the arrival of the population. At the regional level, taking all the province of Burgos, the Provincial Council

plays a significant role in being responsible for social services. This issue is very relevant due to the high presence of the elderly population in this area.

Finally, the role played by SODEBUR in the area should be underlined; a public entity financed by the regional government that is focused on the socioeconomic and environmental development of rural areas in the province of Burgos. It includes actions such as counselling to companies and entrepreneurs, information on grants and incentives, training, good practices and so on.

4.1.5 Access to services and infrastructures

Considering now the data provided by the Statistical Information System of Castilla and León, in the 100 municipalities studied, there were only the following public education centres in the academic year 2022-23: on one side, there are 5 nursery schools with 43 children aged 0-3 years (24 boys and 19 girls). This represents only 1% of the children enrolled in these schools in the provinces of Burgos and Soria (3,834 pupils). Besides, 8 primary schools (CEIP) (from 3-12 years) have a total of 757 pupils enrolled (390 boys and 367 girls), as well as 4 grouped schools with 192 pupils (111 boys and 81 girls). This represents only 3% of the pupils enrolled in this type of school in the provinces of Burgos and Soria (32,954 pupils).

There are 4 secondary and high schools (IES) with 519 students (276 boys and 243 girls). There are no vocational schools, and these students represent 3% of the ones enrolled at this age group in Burgos and Soria (17,021 students). Public education is completed by 5 music and dance schools with a total of 170 students enrolled.

Regarding health issues, in 2022, the population of Burgos and Soria with access to public health services was 98.5% (population with health cards). However, the area doesn't have a hospital or hospital beds. The 100 municipalities have only 4 health centres (8% of the centres in Burgos and Soria), 8 doctor's surgeries (less than 15% of those in the two provinces) and 16 pharmacies (7% in Burgos and Soria).

The social action centres (CEAS) stand out as the basic unit of attention to the entire population around Social Services. They develop their activity in a specific territorial area, called the Social Action area, which refers to a set of province municipalities. Their action is aimed at the entire population: individuals, families, groups, entities and organisations. In the Pinares Burgos-Soria area, there are a total of **5 social action centres**: 3 in municipalities of Burgos, such as Salas de los Infantes, Quintanar de la Sierra and Huerta de Rey, and 2 in municipalities that belong to Soria province: Pinares Sur in Navaleno, and Pinares Norte in Covalada. These centres are crucial for reducing socio-economic disparities, empowering marginalised groups, building social capital, and promoting sustainable development practices in rural areas. They contribute to creating a more inclusive society by offering equal opportunities and addressing specific challenges rural communities face. Overall, Centres for Social Action are instrumental in driving positive social change and fostering well-being, especially in rural contexts where their efforts can be transformative.

The mobility and transport system in the area faces **several challenges**. The region, characterised by its mountainous terrain and scattered rural settlements, experiences significant difficulties in

communication and transportation. Public transport options, such as buses, are limited with scarce services that make it difficult for the daily needs of residents. For instance, in the most remote towns, the elders without driving licenses who need to visit a doctor have several difficulties, although once a week, a doctor and nurse offer medical services from the public health care system. Similarly, trips to the pharmacy or grocery store become difficult, often requiring long waits and planning around sparse bus schedules.

However, it must be remarked that a truck with food (meat, fish, or vegetables) and cleaning products visits these villages twice a week, providing a good service for the inhabitants.

Even though, the lack of reliable public transport exacerbates the isolation of these communities, hindering economic development and contributing to depopulation, as younger generations move quite often to urban centres for better opportunities.

4.1.6 Local policies and instruments

Regarding with policies/instruments/initiatives at the local level to support rural development, it is important to highlight the role of **Local Action Groups (LAGs)** in the territory, piloting the main development Plan for these areas. In the Pinares Burgos-Soria area, two local action groups cover 100 municipalities between Burgos and Soria; however, in Burgos province, the LAGS groups are several:

- **AGALSA-Sierra de la Demanda**¹: Focuses on sustainable development, combating depopulation, creating employment, preserving heritage, and improving residents' quality of life. Manages programs like LEADER, funded by European, national, and regional sources.
- **A.D.R.I. Ribera del Duero Burgalesa**²: Promotes endogenous and sustained development, maintains rural population, increases income and welfare, conserves resources, and mobilises the community and administrations for economic support.
- **ADECOAR**³: Improves life quality in the Arlanza region through Rural Development Programs and initiatives related to tourism, strategic planning, and entrepreneurship.

In Soria, the groups are two LAGs:

- **ASOPIVA**⁴: Formed by town councils, associations, companies, and individuals to address depopulation and develop the Pinares el Valle de Soria and Burgos region using LEADER program resources.
- **Tierras Sorianas del Cid**⁵: Manages Rural Development Programs, provides comprehensive services including information, advice, funding searches, LEADER grant processing, and promotes tourism and local products.

¹ <https://aqalsa.es/>

² <https://riberadeldueroburgalesa.com/inicio/inicioadri/adri/>

³ <https://adecoar.com/index.php>

⁴ <https://www.asopiva.com/asopiva/>

⁵ <https://www.tierrasdelcid.es/>

Connected with these organizations' different initiatives such as microcredits, aid for entrepreneurs promoting energy efficiency, or training actions are offered by the Burgos Provincial Council through SODEBUR⁶ and the Office of Innovation against depopulation⁷ in the case of Soria.

Additionally, the **Burgos Rural 2025 Strategic Plan (PEBUR 2025)**, addressed by the Burgos Provincial Council, aims to establish a sustainable rural development model, focusing on digitalisation, innovation, and making rural areas attractive to prevent depopulation.

4.1.7 Social economy

Regarding the **social economy** at the local level, it should be considered that 60% of the Social Economy in Castilla y León is developed in rural areas and represents 10% of the GDP of Castilla y León (CEPES, 2023).

The Spanish Government Council approved at the end of 2023, under the request of the Regional Ministry of Industry, Trade and Employment, the **Strategic Plan for the Promotion of the Social Economy in the autonomous community of Castilla y León 2023 – 2025**, with a budget of 113 million euros (Ministry of Employment and Industry of the Junta of Castilla and León, 2023).

The main purpose of promoting the social economy in Castilla y León is to generate sustainable and quality employment opportunities, especially for those workers with greater difficulties of insertion in the labour market, either due to personal situation or the area where they live. Thus, the strategy focuses on achieving a general objective of promoting and stimulating employment in Castilla y León, both self-employed and employed, through social economy formulas. Accordingly, three specific objectives are set up:

- To promote and disseminate the qualities of social economy formulas.
- To foster and encourage the incorporation into the labour market of people with disabilities and people in a situation or at risk of social exclusion.
- To encourage collective entrepreneurship through social economy formulas.

The plan incorporates up to 27 measures to achieve these objectives.

On the other hand, in Castilla y León, the **Association of Representative Entities of the Social Economy of Castilla y León (ASECYL)** must be stressed. It comprises entities representing the different business models of the Social Economy, such as worker cooperatives, labour companies, special social initiative employment centres, and insertion companies.

Having more than 12,000 workers throughout Castilla y León, ASECYL assumes the challenge of representing a huge and relevant sector, such as the Social Economy, increasingly supported by the Junta de Castilla y León. ASECYL is made up of several associations whose headquarters are spread

⁶ <https://sodebur.es/emprende-rural/>

⁷ <https://oidsoria.com/>

along the different provinces of the community. The **Association for the Promotion of Insertion Companies of Castilla y León (FECLEI)**, based in Burgos, is one of the most representative.

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5. Vulnerability and social exclusion in the Pinares Burgos-Soria region

5.1 Social exclusion and poverty

When analysing the behaviour of the regional data, Castilla y León has not shown radical transformations between 2015 and 2023. As seen in Figure 6, the territory maintains an average level of living conditions (slightly higher than the national average). Between 2002 and 2023, an improvement in living conditions can be observed when considering the AROPE rate (see Figure 7), which shows a similar situation to that mentioned in the HDI.

However, the data on severe poverty and the percentage of households with low-intensity employment have increased.

Figure 6. Radar of Living Conditions Castilla y León.

Source: INE. Evolution of Quality-of-life indicators (2008-2019)⁸

⁸ Last available reference.

Figure 7. National and Castilla y Leon AROPE Rate.

Source: Canals et al., 2023, p. 3

According to Figure 7, 22.1% of the region's population, a total of 523,000 people, are at risk of poverty and/or exclusion. At the time of publication of this report, Castilla y León ranks ninth in the national total, with a lower incidence of this indicator than other regions. This is rated "upper-middle position" (Canals et al., 2023, p.3). Besides, it should be pointed out that in the whole series analysed (2015-2023), rural areas show a higher AROPE rate than urban areas, as shown below in Figure 8.

When considering the condition of poverty, the habitat of the household and **housing** are indicators of interest. It is particularly noteworthy that in Castilla y León, 34.7% of the poor population spends more than 40% of their income on housing. However, the figure is reduced to 0.9% of non-poor people. Finally, when considering severe poverty (people living in a household with a maximum income of €560), this indicator shows 7.2% in the community (1.7% points below the national total), although it rises slightly again in 2022.

As mentioned before, the AROPE rate is a complex and intersectional indicator. In terms of the risk of poverty, and considering the existing data, it rises up to 17.8%, which means around 421,000 people, of whom 223,000 are women and 198,000 men.

Figure 8. Poverty by habitat in Castilla y León.

Source: Canals et al., 2023, p. 10.

Additionally, when considering age, **the highest poverty rate is that of people under 18 (23.3%)**. In second place, the second highest poverty rate is for people aged 65 and over (18.6%), which in 2022 increased by 8.8%. However, compared to 2015, the poverty rates of the other two age groups have improved – by -4.0 points among the younger population (14.7%) and 3.2 points among those aged 18-64 (16.6%) (Canals et al., 2023 p.7-8). This can be seen in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Poverty by age in Castilla y León.

Source: Canals et al., 2023, p. 9.

Regarding the levels of inequality measured through the Gini Coefficient, Castilla y León is the fifth region with the lowest inequality, with a value of 29.2. This value is 2.8 points lower than the national value (32) and represents a reduction of 0.3 points with respect to the previous year. Finally, and in

relation to the population of foreign origin, the highest AROPE values are found among people over 16 years of age who are not from the EU, followed by the non-EU population, according to the data recorded by the Living Conditions Survey (Junta de Castilla y León, 2023, p. 7).

As some authors of reference have pointed out on this topic (Fitoussi and Rossanvallon, 1997), exclusion is an absolute and relational condition, while poverty is rather connected to a state of deprivation (depending on how it is measured, of income or goods and services). Therefore, the notion of vulnerability is a topic that allows us to qualify these absolute views. Vulnerability is linked to social relations in heterogeneous terms. It is not linked to the absence of something but to the lack of a relationship. Hence, a person with an income above the poverty line can be in a vulnerable situation. An example of interest in the territory being worked on is the vulnerability suffered by the elderly in their homes, expressed in residential deprivation or loneliness (Lebrusan, 2022). In these cases, there may not be a situation of income poverty. Still, there is a vulnerability in terms of "high exposure to certain risks and uncertainties, combined with a diminished capacity to protect or defend oneself against them and to cope with these conditions" (UN, 2003).

An important factor being considered in this report is that this condition of vulnerability is not problematised as something linked to the socio-economic structure but rather to **"social" issues: prejudices, traditions, stereotypes, etc.**⁹

5.2 Labour market

The active population (between 16-64 years of age) rises in the Pinares region to 59%, a task very similar to Spain (58.6%) but a bit lower than in Castilla and León (62.1%). Regarding unemployment, the task for the Pinares- Burgos area is 4.2% in 2023 according to data provided by its LAG. A very low one comparing to Spain that rises to 11% for that year. However, it should be considered the shadow economy in the care sector and agriculture, and among the migrant population. Besides, half of the unemployed are over 50 years old, and the highest unemployment rate is in the service sector, being also an area where most people are employed. However, due to the emigration of young people, enterprises have problems in recruiting qualified people within the territory.

5.3 Access to services

In this context, it is interesting to highlight that associationism, as such, and the expansion of social capital, even in these depopulated and rather remote territories, show an important social fabric and relations. Linked to this, the total number of associations registered in Castilla y León and their location in the different provinces (the Register of the Junta de Castilla y León) shows 37,302 registered associations in the region, being León, Valladolid, Burgos and Salamanca the provinces with the highest number of associations, according to the data available on the Portal of the Junta de Castilla y León.

⁹ It is interesting to consider that social organisations generally avoid using the term "vulnerable groups" precisely because of this disconnection from the socio-economic structure.

It should be mentioned that it cannot be definitively established whether the higher number of associations in these provinces relies on their population density and/or other socio-demographic and socio-cultural characteristics. Regarding the location of the associations in each of the provinces, it can be observed that, apart from the province of Valladolid, more than half of the associations are located outside the capital in the other ones. Thus, this shows the relevance of the associative fabric in rural and/or semi-rural areas of Castilla y León.

Besides that, the information obtained from the interviews carried out with different key informants linked to social and cultural associations it has been possible to draw up a list of the **main needs of the territory**.

One of the main problems frequently pointed out is, as has been mentioned earlier, the **inadequate transport infrastructure**, which links small towns to each other and to medium-sized or main cities, such as Burgos and Soria. The lack of transport limits movement within the territory, having serious consequences in several respects. This lack of mobility (including the difficulty of getting a driving license) and the reduction of education possibilities affect mainly groups such as **young women**. Women, as a social group, are fundamental in rural areas, especially because of their numerical presence and functionality. Still, they encounter barriers in two ways: displacement (mobility) and the condition of "foreigner" for many of them in the legal sense of the term: the processes of obtaining citizenship are often long and make these territorial links much more complex.

It is important to highlight the countries of origin of the population in general, which are mentioned in the in-depth interviews carried out with stakeholders: Bulgaria, Morocco, Latin American and Caribbean countries, with special mention of Honduras. The migration chain is different depending on the origin. Thus, in the case of people from Morocco, migration tends to be staggered: first, the male and then the family. In the case of the Latin American population, women tend to migrate (young and middle-aged), and they also act as heads of household. In these cases, women are particularly involved in care work (this is reflected in the discourse). There is some mention of the presence of people with origins in other Eastern countries linked to forestry activities (timber).

Analysing the discourses, **migration** is referred to as a problem-obstacle, not only due to its implications in terms of broad social mobility but also because of the "vicious circle" that might represent people who want to stay in the territory but cannot find a) conditions of habitability, b) mobility and transport, and 3) legal regularisation. Together with migrants, the young local population is also frequently mentioned. However, with much less emphasis on maintaining the need of rural areas for young people to stay and live in the territory or even return to it.

However, housing shortages are another key issue. With less weight in the story appears the issue of the **lack of technicians**, also pointing out that "The best resource is the technician". The arrival of new residents also increases the demand for people who approach the CEAS because they need a mediator in a context that is somewhat forgotten by the public administration in general. This institution is a point of contact with the community based on the detection of the needs. This qualitative mapping directly relates to the data described in the first section and completes the scenario of vulnerabilities present in the intervention territory.

6. Assets and potentials in the region

According to all the information provided throughout the report, this last section has tried to stress and summarize the opportunities and assets of the Pinares region. On one side, this is an area with exceptional natural resources (stone and wood), and cultural values that need to be considered and empowered in the economic strategy. The area has a deeply rooted forestry sustainable forest management that gives it great potential in the forest bioeconomy: ecosystem services and biomass. Besides, although tourism has been a common resource, in the last years a big effort has been made to provide new routes (either historical and environmental ones). At the same time, the territory with a good quality of life; nature, peace and nature environment. Besides, there is a strong sense of rootedness and belonging within local community, not only among residents but also from those who have a strong link to their locality (stay during weekends and so on). On the institutional side, public ownership of forests allows municipalities' intervention in forest management, creating programs for the rehabilitation and improvement of the building stock in rural areas. Together with that, there is industrial traditions in various sectors: textile, food, wood, etc., encourage the European and national promotion of new productive models articulated around the budgets of the circular economy. However, the main problems in to find qualified workers to join these companies.

Informally, **community networks** play a pivotal role, as neighbours often band together to share resources and provide mutual aid. Residents frequently use informal carpooling arrangements and pool transportation resources to access essential services in neighbouring towns. Additionally, many individuals keep their own home gardens or access to local markets (the example of the truck with food) to mitigate food access issues. Furthermore, social media platforms are crucial communication tools, enabling residents to coordinate assistance and share information about available services. On a formal level, efforts done by local governments include initiatives such as mobile healthcare units and periodic visits by medical professionals, aiming to bridge the gap in healthcare access. Community centres also play a vital role by providing essential services and acting as hubs for distributing resources and support programs for vulnerable populations.

On the other hand, there remain obstacles that make the settlement of new residents difficult (especially young people and women). One of the main issues is public transport services, which remain sparse and insufficient, failing to serve these remote areas adequately. While efforts to provide subsidised or volunteer-based transport services exist, they often struggle to meet the demands of the population, especially the elderly, who rely heavily on public transport for essential services. Despite attempts at improvement, bus schedules continue to be infrequent and inconvenient, exacerbating the isolation of communities and hindering access to vital resources. The only transportation that works properly is the one oriented to take students to schools. Also, **healthcare services** face similar challenges, with telemedicine serving as a partial solution but still limited in reach and effectiveness. Health outreach programs, while beneficial, struggle to overcome the barriers posed by geographical isolation and inadequate infrastructure. Though implemented, economic and social support measures often fall short of alleviating the deep-rooted economic vulnerabilities prevalent in the “España Vacía” or “Spain Emptied”. EU-funded projects such as ‘RuralCare’ – INTEGRATED SOCIAL AND

HEALTH CARE IN THE HOME AT RURAL SCALE of EASI (2014-2020) EMPLOYMENT AND SOCIAL INNOVATION PROGRAMME provide a great deal of economic and social support in this area. **Subsidies and grants**, while provided, are insufficient to address the systemic issues of unemployment and economic stagnation. Community development projects face hurdles due to limited funding and a lack of coordinated efforts, impeding progress towards enhancing resilience and revitalising the region. It becomes evident that institutional and service tools, while necessary, must be substantially bolstered and tailored to the unique challenges faced by communities like those in Pinares Burgos-Soria.

6.1 Strategies or cooperations to reduce inequalities

Local Cooperatives: By promoting fair income distribution and providing collective bargaining power, cooperatives help reduce economic disparities among members.

Partnerships: Collaborations between local businesses, NGOs, and government agencies focus on creating employment and training opportunities. These partnerships often result in projects that enhance local infrastructure, such as improving road access and internet connectivity.

Public bodies and civil society organisations frequently collaborate on initiatives aimed at social inclusion and economic development. Examples include joint community projects, public-private partnerships, and forums for local development planning. Initiatives such as community centres, cultural events, and local festivals are often co-sponsored by public entities and NGOs, fostering social cohesion and cultural preservation.

The region hosts several cooperatives and social enterprises, particularly in sustainable forestry, agriculture, and eco-tourism. These organisations not only provide employment but also focus on environmental sustainability.

Approximately 10-15 social economy organisations operate in the area, employing around 50-100 people. Their activities include sustainable forestry (NACE A02), rural tourism (NACE I55), and organic farming (NACE A01).

In the Pinares region, various social innovations reduce vulnerability and drive sustainable development. Eco-tourism initiatives and renewable energy projects capitalise on natural resources, fostering income generation and environmental awareness. Sustainable forestry practices and local markets bolster the economy while preserving the environment. Investments in digital connectivity and community programs further enhance resilience and youth engagement, reflecting the region's commitment to inclusive rural development.

7. Conclusions and potential focus of the MAP

The Pinares Burgos-Soria region, comprising over 100 municipalities, faces rural challenges such as population ageing and youth exodus. The lack of basic services like healthcare, transportation, and education accelerates depopulation. However, locals are working to revitalise the area through cultural, business, and social initiatives. The "return to the village" trend is growing, being quite relevant to the retirement migration phenomenon and the influence of foreign migration. The region's natural resources, including mountains, pine forests, and landscape, offer opportunities for projects like active tourism, local product companies, worker cooperatives, and community associations.

Since the study area is quite large, the approaches that can be given to the MAP are wide-ranging. One possibility contemplated in the MAP is the creation of cooperatives that represent important sectors of the rural population and allow them to organise themselves to improve their work, their representativeness, or their role in the market and commercial network (Farmers' cooperatives, wood cooperatives, entrepreneurial women's or youth cooperatives...).

Social projects have a special place in the MAP: volunteer groups, support associations for the most vulnerable collectives, projects that improve the services and aids these collectives receive in the rural environment, and initiatives that contemplate the integration and social and labour inclusion... Without forgetting the development of cultural and dynamising projects as well as emerging enterprises that take as raw material the area's resources and develop circular economy models. These initiatives, in addition to mobilising and revitalising the territory, generate a labour niche that can and should be filled with the inhabitants of rural areas, providing job opportunities with the consequent settlement of the population in the villages.

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9. Partners

